

Does the transnational solution manage to cross borders? A bibliographic analysis of English and Chinese language literature citing Bartlett and Ghoshal's seminal book

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Abstract:

Among the most highly cited books in the international business literature, 'Managing across borders: The transnational solution' by Bartlett and Ghoshal (1989) discusses the conflicting pressures faced by firms outside of their domestic markets. We complement impact metrics of this seminal work with qualitative insight. Taking a sociology-of-knowledge perspective, we utilize bibliographic methods to explore how the book's transnationality construct influences the scholarly literature in two of the world's most widely spoken languages. Our further analysis of 888 English language papers and 387 Chinese language works published from 2001 to 2018 reveals that only a small fraction of citing works deeply engages with the book, that a large fraction cite it for no apparent reason, and that the vast majority of works does not help readers distinguish the 'transnational solution' from international, multinational or global strategies. We identify four categories of citing works and discuss their respective implications for the understanding of the transnationality construct. We conclude with reflections on our study's limitations and contributions, and provide suggestions for further research on the sociology of knowledge (and ignorance) in the field of international business.

Keywords:

International, global, multinational, transnational, strategy, business, China, bibliographic analysis

跨国解决方案是否能跨越国界？对引用 Bartlett 和 Ghoshal 经典著作的中英文文献的文献学研究

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摘要

Bartlett 和 Ghoshal 的《跨越国界管理：一个跨国解决方案》是国际商务领域被引次数最多的文献之一。该书讨论了企业在国外市场中所面临的两种相互冲突的压力。在对于此书影响研究中，我们通过定性研究视角完善了定量分析的不足。本文从知识社会学的角度出发，运用文献学方法，探讨该书所阐述的跨国性概念是如何影响世界上使用人口最多的两种语言的学术文献的。本文进一步分析发现，在 2001-2018 年间发表的 888 篇英文文献及 387 篇中文文献中，只有很小一部分文章引用了 Bartlett 和 Ghoshal 的书并显示了对其深刻的理解，而很大的一部分文章属于无明显目的性的随意引用。并且，绝大部分文章并未帮助读者将“跨国解决方案”与国际战略、多国战略和全球战略进行区分。本文将所有已引用 Bartlett 和 Ghoshal 著作的文献分成了四类并依此分别讨论其在理解跨国性概念上的影响。最后，本文对此研究的贡献和局限性进行了总结，并就国际商务领域知识社会学的进一步发展提出了建议。

关键词

国际化战略，全球战略，多国战略，跨国战略，国际商务，中国，文献学分析